

Quanti Farm

**DIGITAL INNOVATION
ACADEMY**

quantifarm.eu

FACTSHEET #6

Funded by
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WHAT IS IT?

The QuantiFarm Digital Innovation Academy (DIA) is a comprehensive capacity building program designed to strengthen the capacities of farm advisors and rural consultants in the field of digital farming. The mission of the Academy is to empower advisors with the knowledge and (technical and soft) skills required to deliver innovative, personalised advisory services related to the selection, uptake and effective application of DATSs, based on the unique needs and specific characteristics of individual farms.

Grounded in real-world insights from QuantiFarm R&I activities and integrating technical, behavioural, and didactical competences within a scalable hybrid framework, the DIA effectively responds to the prevailing mismatch between advisors' existing capabilities and the evolving demands of digital agriculture, also addressing the gaps in existing training provision at both higher and vocational levels.

WHO IS IT FOR?

Farm Advisors and Rural Consultants

seeking to deepen their knowledge of digital farming, and become acquainted with farm oriented-communication and advisory strategies.

Agricultural Educators and Training Providers

seeking to align their offerings and courses with emerging training requirements related to digital agriculture.

Agricultural Students and early-career Advisors

looking to build expertise in data-driven farming practices, stay up-to-date with digital developments and strengthen their employability.

Stakeholders supporting the digital transition

who need to understand how to effectively advise, benchmark, and support farmers using DATSs.

PEDAGOGICAL AND CONTENT

The DIA follows a hybrid Train-the-Trainer and Direct End-User Training scheme, providing knowledge and skills development across five thematic areas:

1. The evolving role of farm advisors in supporting digital uptake.

2. Behavioural determinants affecting DATSs adoption and strategies for effective communication with farmers.

3. Digital Agricultural Technology Solutions (DATSs): Categories, application scope, technical specs, costs, benefits, and sustainability gains.

4. Key factors affecting the effective integration and optimal performance of a digital solution on the farm, including business and operational interventions that maximise the effectiveness of DATSs in practice.

5. How to use the QuantiFarm Toolkit for supporting farmers in making informed decisions on DATSs selection based on their needs.

MAIN FEATURES

Programme specifications

- 7 modules
- 41 learning outcomes
- EQF level 5
- Versatile educational resources (annotated presentation slides, video lectures, case studies, blueprints, hands-on exercises, use case studies, handbooks)
- Formative self-assessment (multiple-choice questionnaire & reflection questions)
- Certificate of attendance (workshop participants)

Four complementary mechanisms

for upskilling farm advisors in the field of digital farming and DATSs, including: a) EU-wide training workshops (TTTs), b) national training sessions with a sectoral, crop/animal-specific focus, c) a digital education platform enabling asynchronous, self-paced learning, and d) integration into formal education, targeting future advisors.

Modular online educational platform

A self-paced, asynchronous educational environment that allow users to engage with the training content according to their own schedules and learning needs. The platform follows a modular structure and provides open access to all educational resources.

Two tailored learning paths

- Train-the-Trainer: for educators & training professionals to scale advisory services.
- End-User Advisor Training: for farm advisors and rural consultants to gain direct skills in digital farming and digital tool usage.

Digital Agriculture Technology Solutions Overview

- 5 DATS categories for crop farming
- 4 DATS categories for livestock farming
- A comprehensive compendium with QuantiFarm DATSs
- Information on more than 500 DATS through the QuantiFarm Toolkit

Practical resources

Hands-on training on how to use the QuantiFarm Toolkit, including the Recommendation System and the Cost-Benefit Calculators, to support farmers in selecting the most suitable digital solutions based on their specific needs and contexts.

Learn
More

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Contact _____

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